

Effectiveness of Cooperative Marketing Strategies in Reducing Post-Harvest Losses among Catfish Farmers in Delta State, Nigeria

Veronica Uchechukwu Ikenga*

*Department of Agricultural Economics, Faculty of Agriculture, Delta State University, Abraka, Nigeria. <https://orcid.org/0009-0005-7504-095X>

Sarah Enwa

Department of Agricultural Economics, Faculty of Agriculture, Delta State University, Abraka, Nigeria. <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-4115-1836>

Agatha Oghenemine Edewor

Department of Agricultural Economics, Faculty of Agriculture, Delta State University, Abraka, Nigeria. <https://orcid.org/0009-0009-8532-8278>

Precious Omesiri Abushe

Department of Agricultural Extension, Faculty of Agriculture, Delta State University, Abraka, Nigeria. <https://orcid.org/0009-0005-2697-1336>

Ogheneovo Akpogheneoyibo-Owigho

Department of Agricultural Economics, Faculty of Agriculture, Southern Delta University, Ozoro
<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-1411-0916>

*Corresponding author email: kenga-veronica@delsu.edu.ng

Abstract

Background of the Study: Group or cooperative operations in agricultural activities especially in marketing holds the potential to improve sales and reduce post-harvest losses of agricultural products usually for small scale farmers.

Objectives of the Study: The study sought to ascertain whether the strategies of cooperative marketing can reduce post-harvest losses among catfish farmers in Delta State, Nigeria.

Methodology: The study made use of the descriptive survey research design. A structured questionnaire was used to collect data from 385 respondents, and data were analysed with both descriptive and inferential statistics, including multiple regression analysis. Results were presented in tables.

Results: The findings revealed that market information sharing ($\beta = -0.213$, $p = 0.000$), joint marketing ($\beta = -0.184$, $p = 0.000$), price negotiation ($\beta = -0.267$, $p = 0.000$), provision of storage facilities ($\beta = -0.089$, $p = 0.030$), and transportation assistance ($\beta = -0.198$, $p = 0.000$) significantly reduced post-harvest losses. The model had a strong explanatory power ($R^2 = 0.731$, $F = 73.509$, $p < 0.01$), confirming that cooperative marketing strategies effectively mitigated post-harvest losses. Price negotiation emerged as the most influential factor, ensuring that farmers received fair compensation and minimised losses due to distress sales. However, inadequate storage facilities were identified as a critical challenge.

Unique Contribution: This study has provided data for understanding the impact of cooperative in promoting effective marketing in agriculture and addressing the perennial problem of post-harvest losses.

Conclusion: Cooperative marketing are helpful in lowering post-harvest.

Key Recommendation: The study recommended strengthening cooperative societies, improving market information systems, investing in storage infrastructure, and enhancing extension services to maximise the benefits of cooperative marketing strategies.

Keywords: Cooperative marketing strategies, post-harvest losses, catfish farming, market information sharing, joint marketing

Introduction

Agriculture is one of the key sectors for socioeconomic development in nations and Nigeria is no exception. Agriculture plays a significant role in employment generation, food security, and economic growth. In the sector, aquaculture has developed as an important subsector, and catfish farming is considered a subsector within it. As such, with the favourable climatic conditions and abundant water resources, Delta State has become a hot spot for catfish farming and hence has become the source of livelihood for smallholder farmers in the area (Oyita & Aberji, 2024; Olaniyi et al., 2024; Nwabueze, 2024).

Post-harvest losses in agricultural production are a very important factor, especially in aquaculture. These losses reduce the farmer's income and food security since a greater portion of the fish harvested is lost during processing, storage, and marketing. These losses are influenced by inadequate infrastructure, lack of access to efficient markets, and limited knowledge of effective marketing strategies (Bukola, 2018). Cooperative societies have been recognised as a viable mechanism for addressing many of the challenges faced by farmers, including reducing post-harvest losses and improving market access (Akinrotimi, 2018).

In assessing the roles which cooperatives play in assisting farmers, it is clear that they render many contributions in several ways. By so doing through the sharing of market information, farmers are able to make right choices on prices and timing for sale, thus minimising distress sales (Obayelu et al., 2016). Integrated marketing communication also contributes to improving bargaining power, making bulk purchases at a lower cost and minimising losses (Adekola & Dokubo, 2017).

Price negotiation through cooperatives allows for maintaining affordable prices and minimising losses due to price fluctuations (Gbigbi & Achoja, 2019). Cold storage services by the cooperatives help to preserve fish to the desired quality by avoiding deterioration (Ikenga, et al., 2023). Facilitating transport serves the purpose of timely delivery so that the farmer can avoid additional loss due to delayed delivery (Ajibade, 2022).

In Nigeria, there has been increased encouragement of catfish farmers to adopt cooperative marketing strategies in efforts towards responding to the challenges faced by the farmers. This encompasses bulk promotion of the processed products, adding value through processing and forming direct channels to reach imagined superior markets like supermarkets, restaurants and export markets (Ajibade et al., 2022). It thereby helps in reducing post-harvesting losses, through which the cooperatives improve the whole chain in order to make farming of catfish in the country more sustainable.

Catfish farming has grown to be an important source of income for smallholder farmers in Delta State, considering the high demand for catfish in both local and regional markets. Despite the rise in aquaculture engagements, post-harvest losses have remained one of the essential constraints that, in most instances, are escalated through poor coordination among farmers and individualistic approaches to marketing. Studies such as Adekola and Dokubo (2017), Gbigbi and Achoja (2019) and Ikenga et al. (2023) have attested that cooperative societies were able to surmount these problems through consolidating resources, facilitating the sharing of knowledge, and the ability to get better access to markets. However, how such marketing strategies have been able to address post-harvest losses in catfish farming has not been fully explored.

Most past studies generally relate to agricultural cooperatives without focusing on the peculiar post-harvest challenges that confront catfish farmers. For instance, Obayelu et al. (2016) investigated socioeconomic determinants of profitability of fresh fish marketing in Ogun State, Nigeria, with emphasis on profitability but limited insight into the reduction of post-harvest losses. Akinrotimi (2018) identified the role of cooperatives in developing fish farming activities in some LGAs within Rivers State, Nigeria, but did not analyse which marketing strategies to be adopted by the cooperative societies in order to lessen such losses. However, Bukola (2018) assessed post-harvest losses, especially among the coastal region of fish farming, revealing that there were inadequate infrastructures and failed to suggest cooperative marketing as a solution to these losses. Though Folorunso et al. (2021) reported the financial constraints facing fish farmers, the study offered few solutions for addressing marketing interventions.

While Obayelu et al. (2016) and Adekola and Dokubo (2017) indicated that cooperatives can be a means to enhance access to markets and reduce inefficiency along the value chain, they lacked enough empirical evidence that specifically relates to catfish farming in Delta State. This, therefore, calls for a critical analysis of cooperative marketing strategies and how these can be used to reduce post-harvest losses. Lack of focused research on the issue is one limitation to developing sustainable interventions that can help the catfish farmers in Delta State. Such a study will be important in bringing useful insights into the operational dynamics of cooperatives and their potential role in addressing some of the critical challenges, including insufficient storage, inefficient transportation, and access to only low-value markets.

This study seeks to fill this gap by assessing the contribution of cooperative marketing strategies to post-harvest loss reduction, hence improving livelihoods and economic growth, as well as food security in the region

Objectives of the Study

The main objective of the study is to effectiveness of cooperative marketing strategies in reducing post-harvest losses among catfish farmers in Delta State, Nigeria. the specific objectives of the study are to:

- i. identify the cooperative marketing strategies employed by catfish farmers in Delta State.
- ii. examine the extent of post-harvest losses experienced by catfish farmers in the study area; and
- iii. determine the effect of cooperative marketing strategies on the extent of post-harvest losses among catfish farmers in the study area.

Hypothesis of the Study

The following null hypothesis guided the study:

HO₁: Cooperative marketing strategies have no significant effect on the extent of post-harvest losses among catfish farmers in Delta State.

Materials and Method

Study Area

Delta State is one of the states in the southern region of Nigeria. It falls between latitudes 5°30'00"N and 6°30'00"N and longitudes 5°30'00"E and 6°30'00"E. The state is estimated to fall within an area of 16,842 square kilometres and is bounded by Edo State to the north, Ondo State to the northwest, Anambra State to the northeast, Bayelsa State to the southeast, and the Atlantic Ocean to the south. Delta State comprises 25 Local Government Areas, and most of its inhabitants are engaged in one form of agriculture or another, including aquaculture, such as catfish farming (Delta State Ministry of Agriculture, 2021). The climatic condition of the state is tropical rainforest, which is characterised by two seasons: the rainy season, which lasts from April to October, and the dry season, covering the period from November to March. Annual rainfall ranges between 2000mm and 3000m while the average temperature stands at 270 C (NIMET, 2022). The major river is River Niger and several creeks are also found in the State. With the support from these water bodies, aquaculture is prominent. The fact that it is strategically located and near markets makes it an ideal location for this study on cooperative marketing strategies among catfish farmers.

Population, Sampling Technique, and Sample Size

The population for this study comprises all registered catfish farmers across the 25 LGAs of Delta State. According to the Delta State Catfish Farmers Association (2023), there are approximately 10,500 registered catfish farmers in the State.

Using registered farmers ensures data is collected from active participants, reducing the risk of including non-representative respondents. The sample size was determined using the Yamane formula:

$$n = \frac{N}{1 + N(e^2)} \dots \dots \dots (1)$$

Where:

n = required sample size

N = population size (10,500)

e = margin of error (5%)

$$n = \frac{10500}{1 + 10500(0.05^2)} = 385 \text{ respondents}$$

A multi-stage sampling technique was employed to select respondents in order to ensure broad representation. In the first stage, Delta State was stratified into its three agricultural zones (Delta North, Delta Central, and Delta South). In the second stage, 5 LGAs were purposively selected from each agricultural zones based on their high concentration of catfish farmers. These LGAs include Oshimili North, Aniocha South, Ndokwa West, Ika South, and Ukwuani (Delta North); Ughelli North, Sapele, Okpe, Ethiope East, and Uvwie (Delta Central); and Warri South, Burutu, Bomadi, Isoko North, and Patani (Delta South). In the third stage, 7 communities were purposively selected from each LGAs based on their high concentration of catfish farmers. In the fourth stage, a simple random sampling technique was used to select 11 catfish farmers from each of the communities. This gave a total of 385 respondents that was used for the study. This structured approach ensures that the sample is representative, geographically diverse, and reflective of catfish farming realities in Delta State.

Data Collection

Primary data were collected using a structured questionnaire designed to capture information on cooperative marketing strategies, post-harvest losses, and related variables. The questionnaire was validated through expert reviews and pre-tested on a sample of 30 farmers outside the study area to ensure reliability (Cronbach's alpha = 0.82). Data collection involved field visits and interviews, with trained enumerators assisting in administering the questionnaires

Data Analysis

The collected data were analysed using both descriptive and inferential statistics. Descriptive statistics such as frequencies, percentages, means, and standard deviations were used to summarize the data. Inferential statistics, such as regression analysis was employed to test the effectiveness of cooperative marketing strategies in reducing post-harvest losses. All analyses were conducted using Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 26.0.

Model Specification

The effectiveness of cooperative marketing strategies in reducing post-harvest losses was assessed using a multiple regression model specified as follows:

$$Y = \beta_0 + \beta_1X_1 + \beta_2X_2 + \beta_3X_3 + \beta_4X_4 + \beta_5X_5 + \beta_6X_6 + \epsilon_i \dots \dots \dots (2)$$

Where:

Y = Post-harvest losses (percentage)

β_0 = Intercept

β_1 to β_4 = Coefficients of independent variables

X₁ = Market information access: Measured using a 4-point Likert scale (1 = Strongly disagree to 4 = Strongly agree).

X₂ = Storage facilities: Measured using a 4-point Likert scale

X₃ = Joint marketing: Measured using a 4-point Likert scale

X₄ = Price bargaining power: Measured using a 4-point Likert scale

X₅ = Educational level: measured by nominal value of No Formal Education (1), Primary Education (2), Secondary Education (3), and Tertiary Education (4)

X₆ = Access to extension services: measured by dummy value of Yes (1) and No (0)

ϵ = Error term

Limitations of the Methodology

Thus, the following are some of the limitations encountered in the course of the structured methodology adopted for this study: The purposive sampling of the LGAs and communities potentially introduced sampling bias, which was controlled by using data from the Delta State Catfish Farmers Association. Non-response bias was controlled through engagement of skilled enumerators who developed good rapport with farmers and also followed them up to ensure high response rates. The 30 farmers from outside the study area participated in pre-test, and feedback from the experts also helped in refining the questionnaire. The Cronbach Alpha Coefficient was 0.82, indicating the reliability of the tool used. Potential challenges of accessibility especially in the remote areas were tackled by assigning enumerators who were conversant with the terrain and altering the time of data collection.

Results And Discussions

Socioeconomic Characteristics of The Respondents

According to the result in Table 1, the demographic distribution of catfish farmers in Delta State is dominated by males, comprising about 71.7%, while females are 28.3%. This tallies with the finding of Jimoh (2021), who reported that 95.8% of catfish farmers in Kwara State were males, thus establishing the fact that catfish farming is a male-dominated occupation, probably because of the nature of the job, which is very tasking. With the mean age being 39 years, the larger proportion of respondents is in their active years and therefore could be reasonably expected to adopt the cooperative marketing strategies positively. The above trend has been supported by such studies as Akerele et al. (2019), who reported that 40% of fish farmers in Egbeda, Oyo State, were in their active years. The dominance of married respondents, 58.4%, further suggests that family responsibilities may influence farming decisions, including cooperative membership and marketing strategy adoption.

Other very critical socio-economic factors in the household include household size; the mean recorded in the study was 7 persons. The household size may also provide more labor to help with farming and marketing. This factor was expressed by Audu (2023), who asserted that family labor contributes to efficiency in fish marketing.

The education levels are relatively high, with 43.6% of the respondents attaining tertiary education that could enable better financial management and record-keeping, hence engaging in cooperative marketing. This agrees with findings by Nkeme and Frank (2022), who found that 85.6% of fish processors in the South-South zone of Nigeria were literate and hence able to adopt improved marketing techniques.

On farm characteristics, the mean size of the pond was 1,126.6 m², describing small to medium-scale production systems. This agreed with Akerele et al. (2019), who reported that 62.5 percent of catfish farmers in Oyo State had operated on 1-2 plots of land. Small pond size could mean reduced output levels and storage capacity for fish after harvest, hence increased dependence on cooperative marketing strategies to reduce losses. The farming experience showed a mean of 15 years, which suggests that the respondents are indeed experienced in catfish farming and their experiences may affect the effectiveness of cooperative strategies. Akinrotimi (2018) observed that more experienced fish farmers were apt to participate in cooperative societies, entrenching further the underlying importance of experience in marketing decisions.

Access to extension services is one of the major determinants in the adoption of innovations, and as many as 61.0% reported access to extension services. The percentage reported in this current study is fairly high compared to most related studies, such as Tunsisa et al. (2024), who reported that limited access to extension services heightened post-harvest losses in Ethiopia's fish value chain. The extension services are very important in the training of farmers in best post-harvest practices, price negotiation, and benefits accruable from cooperative marketing. From the socioeconomic characteristic analysis of respondents, the use of cooperative marketing strategies has great potential to reduce post-harvest losses among catfish farmers in Delta State for improved profitability and sustainability in the sector.

Table 1: Socioeconomic characteristics of the respondents

Variable	Frequency	Percent	Mean
Gender			
Male	276	71.7	
Female	109	28.3	
Age (years)			
Less than 20	15	3.9	
20 – 30	82	21.3	
31 – 41	120	31.2	39 years
42 – 52	98	25.5	
Above 52	70	18.2	
Marital status			
Single	95	24.7	
Married	225	58.4	
Divorced	32	8.3	
Widowed	33	8.6	
Household size (persons)			
1 – 5	180	46.8	
6 – 10	140	36.4	7 persons

11 – 15	45	11.7	
Above 15	20	5.2	
Educational level			
No formal	28	7.3	
Primary	55	14.3	
Secondary	134	34.8	
Tertiary	168	43.6	
Pond size (Square metre)			
Less than 500 m ²	95	24.7	
500 – 1,000 m ²	120	31.2	
1,001 – 2,000 m ²	105	27.3	1,126.6 m ²
Above 2,000 m ²	65	16.9	
Farming experience (years)			
0 – 10	140	36.4	
11 – 20	130	33.8	15 years
21 – 30	80	20.8	
Above 30	35	9.1	
Access to extension services			
Yes	235	61.0	
No	150	39.0	

Cooperative Marketing Strategies Employed by Catfish Farmers

The findings from Table 2 above show that the cooperative marketing strategies significantly reduce post-harvest losses among catfish farmers in Delta State, Nigeria. Most of the respondents agreed that the sharing of market information (mean = 3.42), joint marketing (mean = 3.18), price negotiation (mean = 3.67), and transportation assistance (mean = 3.52) were effective strategies employed, while the provision of storage facilities was not highly adopted (mean = 2.31). These results illustrate the level at which cooperative marketing strategies influence the efficiency and profitability of catfish farming.

Market Information Sharing: Information sharing in the market, rated at a mean of 3.42, was recognised as strategic needs. This result supports Tunsisa et al. (2024), who noted that the level of market information affected the amount of postharvest physical losses of fish in the value chain of Lake Hawassa. Access to market information increases the chances of farmers making the right decisions on price, demand, and appropriate outlets, thereby minimising losses. Likewise, Jimoh (2021) stressed that marketing services are very important in catfish production, and market information enhances the efficiency and profitability of marketing services. Through real-time information, farmers are better placed to know the market price of fish and sell their fish before it spoils. Additionally, Akinrotimi (2018) noted that cooperative societies also improve the market access for fish farmers by providing important information to the farmers on market trends and directly linking them to buyers. In light of these discoveries, it is evident that the enhanced access to market information by farmers via cooperatives can enhance the minimization of post-harvest losses by enabling farmers to make informed marketing choices based on proper information.

Joint Marketing: Another marketing strategy that received above average rating with a mean score of 3.18 was joint marketing. This suggests that farmers should engage in collective selling to improve on their bargaining powers and to avoid getting affected by volatile markets. In a similar vein, Akerele et al. (2019) observed that the membership in cooperatives enhanced access to markets, funds, and business profitability among fish farmers. Integrated marketing allows farmers to market their produce in large volumes, thus, incurring lower individual marketing costs and possible post-harvest losses. Like any other association, these collective marketing efforts boosted the profitability of fish farming and ensured that any harvested fish arrived in the market faster, thus reducing the spoilage level, according to Nkeme and Frank (2022). Further, joint marketing brought about a decrease in the use of middlemen as these agents end up costing farmers a lot of money due to low prices that they offer. Through this they would be able to earn more revenues and at the same time have greater control over the supply chain due to the removal of unwanted middlemen.

Price Negotiation: The pricing strategy was deemed as having the most influence with the mean score of 3.67 for the price negotiation. This leads to the conclusion that cooperative participation in the price-setting process enhances farmers' incomes and minimizes their risks due to volatile markets. Jimoh (2021) also noted that price reduction measures were important in increasing profitability among catfish farmers since they are usually exploited by other intermediaries through price control mechanisms. Organized pricing also helps farmers to be paid reasonable prices for their crops, thus eradicating chances of having to dispose of their produce through forced sales and in the process, end up with spoiled stocks. Achoja (2020) revealed that fishing groups with bargaining power negotiated better prices for the fish farmers, increasing their earnings and decreasing post-harvest losses. Also, the bargaining of prices by cooperatives enables producers to have prior arrangements with the buyers, so they do not face the challenge of finding markets for their crops once they are ready for harvest.

Provision of Storage Facilities: One strategy was negatively agreed upon and it was the provision of storage facilities with a mean of 2.31. This shows that most catfish farmers operate without proper storage facilities and this escalates the post-harvest losses. According to the study conducted by Audu (2023) which focused on Ondo State, fishermen who operated in the small scale did not have access to ice, or appropriate covering and storage facilities and all these contributed to post harvest losses of fish which in the case of catfish reached 7.76%. In the same vein, Akintola and Fakoya (2017) noted that lack of appropriate preservation techniques, including poor sun-drying and smoking methods, accelerated the losses of fish in Nigeria. Lack of storage facilities forces the fish farmers to sell their produce in the market immediately, which leaves them with no option but to accept low prices for their fish. Precisely, this issue is worsened by faulty electricity supplies that are prevalent in cold storage companies where they are present. Kaminski *et al.* (2020) also pointed out that Zambian female fish processors experienced relatively high levels of post-harvest loss as they have limited access to appropriate storage and preservation methods. Mitigating this problem would also demand an injection of capital in cold storage equipment for cooperatives and proper funding for small-scale fish farmers. In line with this assertion, Nkeme and Frank (2022) called for the setting up of storage centers in the fish farming zones to reduce spoilage or loss and increase profits.

As for the farmers, they could seek to form cooperatives where they could collectively purchase ice-making machines and refrigerated trucks for improving preservation and transport.

Transportation Assistance: The mean score for Transportation assistance was 3.52 For this item, the farmers showed their understanding in having proper means of transport to ensure that losses due to poor means of transport are reduced. The marketing of fresh fish normally means that such fish has to undergo transportation to the markets, and any delay or mishandling of fish can spoilage. A survey conducted in Ondo State by Nkeme and Frank (2022) also established that poor means of transport greatly enhanced deterioration of fish among fishermen thus enhancing post-harvest losses. The study showed that fish marketing was able to remove losses due to better the transport networks and infrastructures. The results of the present study corroborate these findings particularly calling for improvement in the road infrastructure and coordinated transport systems in order to enhance the market access. Besides, Akinrotimi (2018) revealed that cooperative societies were also useful in helping out fish farmers in the state in the way of transport so that fishery products can easily reach the market without much delay. Those who had access to the vehicles owned by the cooperative were able to transport their produce fresh hence reducing on cases of spoilage. Hence, the need for collective investment in transportation infrastructure for effective marketing of the fish.

Table 2: Cooperative marketing strategies employed by catfish farmers

Marketing strategies	Mean	Std. Dev.	Remark
Market Information Sharing	3.42	0.765	Agreed
Joint Marketing	3.18	0.812	Agreed
Price Negotiation	3.67	0.698	Agreed
Provision of Storage Facilities	2.31	0.890	Disagreed
Transportation Assistance	3.52	0.742	Agreed

Mean value ≥ 2.5 is agreed, ≤ 2.5 is disagreed

Extent of Post-Harvest Losses Experienced by Catfish Farmers

From Table 3, it can be seen that post-harvest losses among catfish farmers in Delta State are quite high, averaging 20.3% of the total harvested fish. In this case, it was established that the mean quantity harvested per respondent was 1,152.7kg, out of which 918.5kg was sold/consumed and 234.2 kg was lost. The distribution of the harvested quantity shows that about 35.3 % of the farmers harvested between 500 – 1,000 kg while the 15.3 % harvested above 2,000 kg. Such losses may be attributed to faulty storage mechanisms, poor transport, and cooperative marketing approaches. This is in support of the study carried out by Audu (2023), where he has opined that challenges faced in marketing channels, and constraints in the efficient storage and transportation of fish significantly Influence post-harvest losses in the fish farming industry in Nigeria.

The quantity sold and consumed also highlights the factors that have contributed to the issues experienced by catfish farmers in the marketing of their produce. Overall 34.3% of the farmers sold or consumed between 901 – 1,800 kg while 30.6% could only sell between 400 – 900 kg hence the importance of market access and formation of cooperatives. The study is in line with Akerele *et al.*, (2019) that revealed fish farmers who received loans from the cooperative and the pooled resources in form of associations were likely to record higher levels of profitability and low levels of losses.

This suggests that more cooperation through better bargaining power for purchasing fresh produce and better storage facilities could improve sales and reduce spoilage (Folorunso et al., 2021). The amount lost on an average (234.2 kg) suggests that there is a requirement for intervention among specific segments. In the study, the highest percentage of the farmers (38.2%) incurred losses within the range of 50 – 150 kg while 28.3% lost within the range of 151 – 300 kg. The comparatively high loss rate might indicate a weakness in post-harvest handling, which can be attributed to limited access to cooling facilities and poor logistics networks. Jimoh (2021) noted that price controls or haggling and discounts were critical for enhancing the return on investment in catfish farming as it helped to prevent farmers from incurring heavy losses due to slow sales turnover. Therefore, cooperative marketing strategies which are aimed at stabilizing prices, purchasing in large quantities and distribution could help prevent such losses (Gyan et al., 2020). In general, the study shows the significance of marketing cooperation in minimizing post-harvest losses in catfish farmers' operations. The farmers who adopt measures like marketing integration, bargaining on the price of the produce, and transportation support are likely to incur lower losses. These findings agree with Tunsisa *et al.* (2024) who noted that fish farmers in cooperatives that possessed market information, storage facilities and technology for value addition experienced low post harvest loss. From this it can be inferred that enhancement of cooperative marketing policies cutting across market access, storage, and transportation can potentially cut down losses and enhance the gross revenue on catfish production in Delta State.

Table 3: Extent of post-harvest losses experienced by catfish farmers

Item	Frequency	Percent	Mean	Average percent loss
Quantity harvested (Kg)				
Less than 500	87	22.6		
500 – 1,000	136	35.3		
1,001 – 2,000	103	26.8	1,152.7	
			Kg	
Above 2,000	59	15.3		
Quantity sold/consumed (Kg)				
Less than 400	68	17.7		20.3%
400 – 900	118	30.6		
901 – 1,800	132	34.3	918.5 Kg	
Above 1,800	67	17.4		
Quantity lost (Kg)				
Less than 50	72	18.7		
50 – 150	147	38.2	234.2 Kg	
151 – 300	109	28.3		
Above 300	57	14.8		

Effect of Cooperative Marketing Strategies on the Extent of Post-Harvest Losses Among Catfish Farmers

Results from Table 4 shed useful light on how cooperative marketing strategies have influenced the degree of post-harvest losses among catfish farmers in Delta State, Nigeria. The R-square of

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0.731 implies that about 73.1% of the variation in post-harvest losses is explained by the cooperative marketing strategies, educational level, and access to extension services. That means the model is explaining a high proportion of the determinants of post-harvest loss among catfish farmers. The F-statistic of 73.509 indicates that the overall model is statistically significant, hence the independent variables have jointly had an influence on post-harvest loss. The study therefore rejects the null hypothesis (H_0) which stated that cooperative marketing strategies have no significant impact on the extent of post-harvest losses among catfish farmers in the study area. Furthermore, the Durbin-Watson statistic of 1.946 shows no severe autocorrelation of residuals, hence estimates from the model are reliable.

Effect of Market Information Sharing on Post-Harvest Losses: The coefficient of market information sharing is negative and statistically significant at the 1% level, (coefficient = -0.213, $p = 0.000$), which implies that access to timely and relevant market information significantly decreases post-harvest losses among catfish farmers. This means that when farmers are very aware of prevailing prices in the market, fluctuations in demand, and the potential buyer of their produce, informed decisions can be made on when and where to sell and hence minimize loss. This in essence reduces the problem of overstocking unsold fish by those farmers, often ending in their spoilage when storage is not effective. This again corresponds to a parallel result on Lake Hawassa in which it was revealed that post-harvest loss for the Lake Hawassa fish value chain decreased remarkably following better market information access (Tunsisa *et al.* 2024). In the same vein, Jimoh (2021) reiterates that pricing strategies in catfish farming depend on efficient market information to curtail wastage while maximizing profits. For this reason, strengthening market information systems through digital platforms, cooperative networks, and extension officers are ways to go in minimizing post-harvest losses in Delta State.

Effect of Joint Marketing on Post-Harvest Losses: The coefficient of joint marketing is -0.184, $p = 0.000$, further indicating that farmers belonging to cooperative marketing groups experience reduced post-harvest losses unlike the individual farmers selling directly. This is because through joint marketing, farmers pool their produce so that they may have access to larger markets that will enable them to get good sales terms for their fish products and hence avoid delays that might make their unsold fish spoil. Cooperative marketing has also witnessed a reduction in the exploitation of the individual farmer by middlemen, ensuring that they compete at the best prices and without pressure to sell the fish at cheaper prices due to storage stresses. Empirical evidence to that effect was provided by Akerele *et al.* (2019), since their study on cooperative loans in Oyo indicated that farmers who were members of cooperatives enjoyed heightened profitability and better access to markets. In fact, Achoja (2020) has established that catfish farmers in Delta State who adopt cooperative marketing recorded improved creditworthiness and increased financial stability, which they used to invest in more efficient storage and marketing methods. This, therefore, means that stimulating farmer cooperatives through joint marketing arrangements can go a long way toward improving the efficiency of catfish marketing in Delta State.

Effect of Price Negotiation on Post-Harvest Losses: Price negotiations had a significant impact in reducing post-harvest losses, with a coefficient of -0.267 at $p = 0.000$. This shows that farmers are able to negotiate prices with buyers, securing better deals and reducing spending on unnecessary storage time. Therefore, good price negotiation means that farmers can sell fish at good market prices and do not fall prey to distress sale out of loss aversion.

These results are in agreement with the findings of Jimoh (2021), who reported that the quantity discounting and price negotiation strategies were the only ways of sustaining the profitability status of catfish farming. Akerele *et al.* (2019) also noted that cooperative farmers who had strategic negotiations of prices with bulk buyers suffered lower post-harvest losses compared to farmers who sold individually. With this in mind, cooperatives should offer training in price negotiation skills so that farmers are able to have better prices with minimal post-harvest losses.

Effect of Provision of Storage Facilities on Post-Harvest Losses: Pro-storage facilities had a negative but weak influence on post-harvest loss (coefficient = -0.089, $p = 0.030$). That is, although storage facilities may help to reduce losses, the strength is not as prominent in market-related strategies like price negotiation and joint marketing. Most of the small-scale farmers lack storage infrastructure, and even those who have storage facilities find them inadequate for large volumes of harvested fish. In fact, a study conducted in Ondo State showed that Audu (2023) indicated that small-scale fishermen had massive post-harvest losses due to a lack of storage and cooling facilities. Gyan *et al.* (2020) also identified poor access to refrigeration and ice as some of the causes of high losses in Ghana's fish markets. Improvement would require investment in community-based cold storage facilities and mobile cooling units for the better preservation of fish.

Effect of Transportation Assistance on Post-Harvest Losses: Transport support also showed a very high significance in reducing post-harvest losses, with a coefficient of -0.198 and a p -value of 0.000. This shows that farmers who receive support in transportation can quickly move their produce to the markets, hence reducing chances of spoilage. Bad roads and high costs of transportation are some of the challenges faced by fish farmers in Nigeria due to the inability to deliver fresh fish to buyers of short duration. This agrees with Gyan *et al.* (2020) in Ghana, who identified transportation constrains as among the major reasons for postharvest fish loss in their country. In this regard, Akintola and Fakoya (2017) also emphasized that improving the transport infrastructure could help enhance the sustainability of small-scale fisheries in Nigeria. Hence, subsidized transport schemes for farmers are among the policies that could help improve logistics in transportation and hence reduce post-harvest losses.

Effect of Educational Level and Extension Services on Post-Harvest Losses: The results also indicate that farmers' educational level (-0.074, $p = 0.021$) and access to extension services (-0.146, $p = 0.002$) significantly influence post-harvest losses. Educated farmers are more likely to adopt improved post-harvest handling techniques, such as proper storage, timely marketing, and efficient pricing strategies. Extension services play a critical role in equipping farmers with the necessary skills to reduce losses, including training on post-harvest handling and cooperative marketing strategies. These findings are supported by Achoja (2020), who found that extension services significantly improved fish farmers' marketing efficiency and profitability. Similarly, Nkeme and Frank (2022) highlighted that education and awareness of improved fish processing technologies were key determinants of post-harvest loss reduction in Nigeria's South-South region. Therefore, expanding extension programs and providing continuous farmer education on post-harvest management could lead to significant improvements in the industry.

Table 4: Effect of cooperative marketing strategies on the extent of post-harvest losses among catfish farmers

Variable	Coefficient	Standard Error	t-Statistic	p-Value
Constant	2.547	0.382	6.667	0.000
Market Information Sharing	-0.213***	0.057	-3.737	0.000
Joint Marketing	-0.184***	0.049	-3.755	0.000
Price Negotiation	-0.267***	0.064	-4.172	0.000
Provision of Storage Facilities	-0.089***	0.041	-2.171	0.030
Transportation Assistance	-0.198***	0.053	-3.736	0.000
Educational level	-0.074**	0.032	-2.313	0.021
Access to extension services	-0.146***	0.047	-3.106	0.002
Model Summary				
R-Squared	0.731	F-Statistic	73.509	
Adjusted R-Squared	0.721	Durbin-Watson	1.946	

***, ** are significant at 1% and 5% level respectively

Conclusion and Policy Recommendations

The study confirmed that cooperative marketing strategies indeed help in lowering post harvest loss among catfish farmers in Delta State. The regression analysis revealed that market information sharing, joint marketing, price negotiation, transportation assistance, and storage facilities are valuable techniques to reduce losses. Of these strategies, price negotiation had the most significant impact, which safeguarded farmers from getting worst deals and distress selling. Similarly, cooperative marketing efforts and information exchange assisted in negotiations and better decision making, with allowance for loss of perishability and monetary wastage. Nonetheless, the use of these strategies was considered helpful by the fishermen, though access to storage facilities remained a limitation since farmers were unable to preserve unsold fish properly. This is in line with earlier studies where infrastructure to store produce was cited as a major reason for post-harvest losses in fishery sub sector. This further meant that farmers with higher education level and those who were able to access extension services had low post harvest loss showing that there is need for more training, knowledge of farmers. Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations were made:

- i. Farmer cooperatives, Ministry of Agriculture and NGOs should encourage more farmers to participate in cooperative societies to enhance collective bargaining power.
- ii. The government, private sector, ICT companies and farmer cooperatives should develop digital platforms for real-time price and demand information sharing to help farmers make informed selling decisions.
- iii. The government, donor agencies, farmer cooperatives, and private investors should establish community-based cold storage facilities and encourage cooperative ownership of preservation facilities.
- iv. Ministry of transportation, farmer cooperatives, and private sector should facilitate access to cooperative-owned refrigerated transport vehicles for fish farmers.
- v. Agricultural extension agencies, universities and NGOs should increase training programs on post-harvest management, price negotiation, and marketing strategies.

References

- Achoja, F. O. (2020). Original research article determinants of credit rating of cooperative fish farmers: Evidence from Delta State, Nigeria. *Journal of Agriculture and Food Environment*, 7(2), 45-57.
- Adekola, G., & Dokubo, C. (2017). Co-operative societies and poverty reduction among members for community development in Rivers State, Nigeria. *European Scientific Journal*, 13(8), 250-259.
- Ajibade, Y., Onimisis, M., & Yusuf, A. (2022). Fish processing and marketing among women fish mongers in Ofu Local Government Area, Kogi State, Nigeria. *Journal of Agricultural Science and Practice*, 7(2), 27-35.
- Akerele, E. O., Ilori, A. R., Fadipe, M. O., Oluwasanya, O. P., & Ayodele, J. O. (2019). Effects of cooperative loan on small scale fish farming business in Oyo State, Nigeria. *NIU Journal of Social Sciences*, 5(3), 7-17.
- Akinrotimi, O. (2018). Roles of cooperative societies in aquaculture development: a case study of some Local Government Areas in Rivers State, Nigeria: Roles of cooperative societies in aquaculture development: A Case Study of Some Local Government Areas in Rivers State, Nigeria. *Agricultural Extension Journal* 2(02).132-138 <https://doi.org/10.22377/aextj.v2i02.78>
- Akintola, S. L., & Fakoya, K. A. (2017). Small-scale fisheries in the context of traditional post-harvest practice and the quest for food and nutritional security in Nigeria. *Agriculture & Food Security*, 6, 1-17.
- Audu, A. (2023). *Assessment of marketing channels of smoked fish in Ese-Odo Local Government Area of Ondo State, Nigeria* (Doctoral dissertation, Federal University Of Technology, Akure).
- Bukola, A. O. A. (2018). *Assessment of post-harvest fish losses among small-scale fishermen in Ondo State, Nigeria*. (PhD Dissertation, Universiti Utara Malaysia).
- Delta State Catfish Farmers Association. (2023). *Membership and Production Statistics*. Delta State Catfish Farmers Association Publication.
- Delta State Ministry of Agriculture. (2021). *Annual Agricultural Report*. Delta State Government Press.
- Folorunso, E. A., Rahman, M. A., Sarfo, I., Darko, G., & Olowe, O. S. (2021). Catfish farming: a sustainability study at Eriwe fish farming village in southwest Nigeria. *Aquaculture International*, 29, 827-843.
- Gbigbi, T. M., & Achoja, F. O. (2019). Cooperative financing and the growth of catfish aquaculture value chain in Nigeria. *Croatian Journal of Fisheries*, 77(4), 263-270.

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- Gyan, W. R., Alhassan, E. H., Asase, A., Akongyuure, D. N., & Qi-Hui, Y. (2020). Assessment of postharvest fish losses: The case study of Albert Bosomtwi-Sam fishing harbour, Western Region, Ghana. *Marine Policy, 120*, 104120.
- Ikenga, V. U., Ogisi, O. D., & Gbigbi, T. M. (2023). Profitability of aquaculture by gender in Delta State, Nigeria. *Direct Research Journal of Agriculture and Food Science, 11*(6), 144-152.
- Jimoh, A. A. (2021). *Analysis of Pricing Strategies in Catfish Farming in Kwara State* (Master's thesis, Kwara State University (Nigeria)).
- Kaminski, A. M., Cole, S. M., Al Haddad, R. E., Kefi, A. S., Chilala, A. D., Chisule, G., ... & Ward, A. R. (2020). Fish losses for whom? A gendered assessment of post-harvest losses in the Barotse Floodplain Fishery, Zambia. *Sustainability, 12*(23), 10091.
- Nigerian Meteorological Agency (NIMET). (2022). *Climatic data on rainfall and temperature in Nigeria*. Abuja: NIMET Press.
- Nkeme, K. K., & Frank, N. N. (2022). Improved Fish Processing Technology (IFPT) Utilisation in South-South Nigheria. *Nigerian Journal of Rural Sociology, 22*(2), 6-13.
- Nwabueze, Q. I. (2024). Applying Community Mass Media for the Promotion of Agribusiness in Nigeria. *Mdooter Journal of Communication and Digital Technologies, 1*(1), 13-23. <https://www.mdooterj.com/index.php/mdooterj/article/view/2>
- Obayelu, A. E., Arowolo, A. O., Ibrahim, S. B., & Oderinde, C. O. (2016). Socioeconomic determinants of profitability of fresh fish marketing in Ogun State, Nigeria. *International Journal of Social Economics, 43*(8), 871-883.
- Olaniyi, A. I., Osuafor, O. O., Nwafor, S. C., Edeh, O. U., & Ekeh, . D. U. . (2024). Assessing the Influence of Information and Communication Technology Constraints on Cassava Value Chain Actors in Anambra State. *Torkwase Journal of Agricultural Research, 1*(1), 30-40.
- Oyita, G. E., & Aberji, O. D. (2024). Contribution of Catfish Farming to Household Income in Ukwuani Local Government Area, Delta State, Nigeria. In *e-Proceedings of the Faculty of Agriculture International Conference* (pp. 268-275).
- Tunsisa, T. T., Dadi, K. B., & Melesse, K. A. (2024). Determinants of Postharvest Physical Losses in the Fish Value Chain: Evidence from Lake Hawassa, Sidama National Regional State, Ethiopia. PREPRINT (Version 1) available at Research Square. <https://doi.org/10.21203/rs.3.rs-3947763/v1>